

SICF/SIC STIFFNESS PREDICTION, THERMAL RESIDUAL STRESS AND PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE SIMULATION BY MICRO-MECHANICS MODEL

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ABSTRACT

Ceramic matrix composites (CMCs, e.g. SiC_f/SiC) are applied widely in hot-section components of aeronautics and astronautics. The macroscale mechanical properties of CMCs can be easily obtained by standard tests. Likewise, the thermal residual stress created during preparation can be monitored by experimental means. However, in the material design stage, it will result in waste only through testing validation, and especially a few parameters need to be optimized and determined. Precise virtual simulation technology (VST) is extremely useful on predicting materials' performance and giving optimal strategies to materials designers. Under this mean, the present work is mainly focusing on predicting the macro-stiffness and thermal residual stress (TRS) for SiC_f/SiC composites. 3D micro-structure finite element analysis (FEA) methods are applied to representative volume elements (RVE). Period boundary condition (PBC) is adopted in the RVE to make stiffness prediction, which cannot be utilized in the deformation of thermal expansion. The microscale RVE model can be used to calculate the elastic modulus in fiber direction and two fiber's normal directions, as well as shear modulus of in-plane and out-plane. Distributions of radial, hoop, axial and shear TRS in fiber, interphase and matrix are analyzed profoundly. Besides, in the 3D microscale FEA model specialized for TRS calculation, parameters effects of homogeneous and anisotropic interphase modulus and interphase thickness are investigated. The models are not only adapted to SiC_f/SiC composites, but also to the other fiber toughened CMCs foremost.

1 INTRODUCTION

The excellent performance of high temperature, oxidation and fatigue resistance make SiC_f/SiC composites possess a wide application in many fields such as aero-engine. For example, SiC_f/SiC composites are the key structural materials in the advanced aero-engine hot-section components. Aero-engine structures work under the environment of elevated temperature, mechanical load and oxidation. In the year of 2015, GE company successfully applied SiC_f/SiC composites in the low-pressure turbine rotor of the aero-engine. Computational micromechanics of composites is an emerging tool that is required in virtual materials design (VMD) to address the effect of different parameters involved before materials are manufactured. And this strategy will help avoid unnecessary costs, reducing trial-and-error campaigns leading to fast material developments for tailored properties [1].

Although SiC_f/SiC composites have been studied extensively, the approaches are mainly focusing on the experiments, and the simulations are generally on the basis of mesoscale model and macroscale model. Mital [2] performed detailed finite element analyses on examining how the variability in the local microstructure affected the macroscopic behaviour as well as the local damage initiation and progression. Naouar [3] presents a direct method by using computed tomography to determine finite element models based on the real geometry of the textile reinforcement. Straumit [4] investigates application of the structure tensor, a concept from the image processing field, to determine of the orientations of fibres and to segment the image into the material's components, for the purpose of an

automatic generation of a voxel-based description of the representative volume element. Damage and failure processes in two relatively complex ceramic matrix composite sub-elements are studied by using computational modelling which considers, in a coupled way, both the nonlinear behaviour of plies due to intra-laminar ply damage mechanism as well as the interlaminar delamination mechanism at the ply interfaces [5].

SiCf/SiC composites are fabricated under the elevated temperature by the chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) processing. Due to the extensive mismatch of the coefficients of thermal expansion (CTEs) between the constituents (fibre, interphase and matrix), thermal residual stresses are often generated in the composites upon cooling from processing to room temperatures. The different thermal expansions of material components lead to SiCf/SiC composites exist the thermal residual stress, which is usually obtained by experiment. And TRS are known to have a significant influence on the macroscopic mechanical behaviour of CMCs by determining the stress states. X-ray diffraction (XRD) is considered as the most traditionally used technique for characterizing residual stresses in CMC materials [6] presents an alternative easy-to-apply method to quantify the residual stress state in continuous fibre ceramic matrix composites. Thermal residual stress in the C/SiC was quantified by three different methods of experimental measurement, analytical calculation, and theoretical prediction, and then compared with that in the SiC/SiC [7].

During the process of material design, the scientific basis and theoretical methodology of the microstructure design are still lack. Thus, the present studies focus on investigation on stiffness at different directions and thermal residual stresses by microscale FEA method. Detailed analysis of complex microstructures may provide clues for the material scientists who ‘design the material’ or to structural analysts and designers. The prediction work on the stiffness and TRS is conducted in this paper.

2 MICRO-STRUCTURE FEA THEORY

Finite Element Method (FEM) can dates back to Courant [8], who firstly attempted to apply piecewise continuous function on a series triangle zones and principle of minimum potential energy, to solve the St. Venant torsion problem. FEM practical application starts from Turner et al [9] in the field of elastic mechanics plane problem of aircraft structure analysis. A further discussion on the plane elastic problem was carried out by Clough [10] who proposed the name of FEM for the first time. FEM basic theory is used to construct functional under differential equation and boundary condition, and then obtain energy variation principle of original problem as shown in Eq. (1).

$$\delta\Pi(\mathbf{u})=0 \quad (1)$$

Wherein, \mathbf{u} denotes the unknown field function. And the unknown field function can be expressed by a series trial functions with undetermined parameters. This is called Ritz method as shown in Eq.(2).

$$\mathbf{u} \approx \tilde{\mathbf{u}} = \sum_{i=1}^n N_i \mathbf{a}_i = \mathbf{N}\mathbf{a} \quad (2)$$

Wherein, \mathbf{N} denotes the known functions. The variation functional equaling to zero amounts to differentiate the functional by all of the undetermined parameters, as shown in Eq. (3). And for most of engineering problems, in the quadratic function \mathbf{u} and its differential coefficient exponentiation are not higher than 2. Therefore, Eq. (3) degrades into linear equations as shown in Eq. (4).

$$\delta\Pi = \frac{\partial\Pi}{\partial\mathbf{a}_1} \delta\mathbf{a}_1 + \frac{\partial\Pi}{\partial\mathbf{a}_2} \delta\mathbf{a}_2 + \dots + \frac{\partial\Pi}{\partial\mathbf{a}_n} \delta\mathbf{a}_n = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial\Pi}{\partial\mathbf{a}} \equiv \mathbf{K}\mathbf{a} - \mathbf{P} = \mathbf{0} \quad (4)$$

3 STIFFNESS PREDICTION

3.1 Periodic boundary condition

The periodic boundary condition equations of displacement field were proposed by Suquet [11] early as shown in Eq. (5).

$$u_i = \bar{\varepsilon}_i x_k + u_i^* \quad (5)$$

Wherein, $\bar{\varepsilon}_i$ denotes the average strain in the RVE, x_k denotes the coordinate at any point of the RVE, and u_i^* is the modified periodic displacement. Generally, RVE is chose as a cuboid as shown in Fig. 1, which simplifies the periodic problems to the relations between parallel surfaces, edges and corner points. The displacement difference between two parallel surfaces + and - can eliminate the modified periodic displacement as shown in Eq.(6). For example, displacement difference between point o and o' lies in surface Left and Right can be expressed by Eq.(6).

$$u_i^+ - u_i^- = \bar{\varepsilon}_{ik} (x_k^+ - x_k^-) = \bar{\varepsilon}_{ik} \Delta x_k \quad (6)$$

PBC equations between surfaces contain Top & Bottom, Front & Back, and Left & Right, excepting edges and corner points, as shown in Eq. (7), Eq. (8) and Eq. (9) respectively. The relations between displacement difference and engineering strain are shown in equations.

Figure 1: Cuboid RVE including corresponding surfaces, edges and points.

$$\begin{cases} u|_{x=L_x} - u|_{x=0} = L_x \varepsilon_x \\ v|_{x=L_x} - v|_{x=0} = 0 \\ w|_{x=L_x} - w|_{x=0} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{cases} u|_{y=L_y} - u|_{y=0} = L_y \gamma_{xy} \\ v|_{y=L_y} - v|_{y=0} = L_y \varepsilon_y \\ w|_{y=L_y} - w|_{y=0} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{cases} u|_{z=L_z} - u|_{z=0} = L_z \gamma_{zx} \\ v|_{z=L_z} - v|_{z=0} = L_z \gamma_{yz} \\ w|_{z=L_z} - w|_{z=0} = L_z \varepsilon_z \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Wherein, L_x , L_y , L_z denote the cuboid RVE length along x, y, z directions. u, v, w are respectively displacement along direction x, y, z.

PBC equations between edges include ⑨&⑩, ⑨&⑪, ⑨&⑫, ①&③, ①&⑤, ①&⑦, ②&④, ②&⑥, ②&⑧.

3.2 FEA of regular fibers RVE

Generally, there are six engineering strains, $\varepsilon_x, \varepsilon_y, \varepsilon_z, \gamma_{xy}, \gamma_{yz}, \gamma_{zx}$. It is assumed that characteristics of each of the component materials are known. In the material design stage, it is hoped that the material stiffness can be obtained accurately. Although fiber direction stiffness can be easily deduced by the Young's modulus and the volume fractions of fiber, interphase and matrix, other two perpendicular direction stiffnesses and three shear modulus prediction cannot be deduced easily. Furthermore, material component local stress cannot be predicted. Based on RVE ideology with PBC, a 3D micro-structure FEA methodology is proposed to solve these problems.

The 3D micro-structure FEA model is built and calculated in Abaqus/standard. RVE size is obtained statistically from the micro-paragraph of SiC_f/SiC composites. And Table 1 shows the RVE length, width, height and material components size. Mechanical properties of SiC_f/SiC composites components are shown in Table 2.

The RVE FEA model shown in Fig. 2 is composed of fiber, interphase and matrix. The FEA mesh size is 0.25 μ m and the element type is C3D8R in Abaqus/standard. In the model, material coordinate systems are cylinder systems, which define radial, hoop and axial directions for fibers, the surrounding interphase and matrix. The four quarter fibers and the surrounding interphase at the corners have independent cylinder systems.

RVE size/ μ m			Components size/ μ m			
Length	Width	Height	Fiber diameter	Interphase thickness	Fiber distance at 0°directoin	Fiber distance at 45°directoin
19.8	19.8	19.8	12.5	0.5	19.8	14.0

Table 1: Micro-structure size of SiC_f/SiC composites

SiC fiber			BN interphase			SiC matrix		
E/GPa	G/GPa	ν	E/GPa	G/GPa	ν	E/GPa	G/GPa	ν
383	140	0.25	50	20.8	0.2	350	140	0.25

Table 2: Mechanical properties of SiC_f/SiC composites components

Figure 2: SiC_f/SiC RVE geometry and finite element mesh.

The displacement loading(0.1 μ m) is applied to RVE model, which contains $\varepsilon_x, \varepsilon_y, \varepsilon_z, \gamma_{xy}, \gamma_{yz}, \gamma_{zx}$ respectively. Due to the symmetry of micro-structure, ε_y equals to ε_z , and γ_{xy} equals to γ_{zx} . The calculation result nephogram of deformation, von-Mises stress, radial stress, hoop stress, axial stress and three shear stress are shown in Table 3. According to the calculated results, the deformation along fiber direction(ε_x) is uniform, whereas other direction deformations are not. von-Mises equivalent stress referred Eq. (10), gives us that stress in the interphase and intersection between fibers especially while the fibers distance is very close.

$$S_{Mises} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{(S_{11} - S_{22})^2 + (S_{22} - S_{33})^2 + (S_{33} - S_{11})^2 + 6(S_{12}^2 + S_{23}^2 + S_{13}^2)} \quad (10)$$

For each loading direction, six different stress variables are shown in Table 3. The foregoing literature usually provide radial, hoop and axial stresses, and do not contain the shear stresses. The present calculation work provides all of the stresses, some of which approximate to zero. For the readability, the stresses vs. displacements are expressed as matrix form as shown in equation (11).

$$\sigma_{micro-structure} = \begin{matrix} \varepsilon_x & \varepsilon_y & \varepsilon_z & \gamma_{xy} & \gamma_{yz} & \gamma_{zx} \\ \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{rr} & \sigma_{rr} & \sigma_{rr} & 0 & 0 & \sigma_{rr} \\ \sigma_{hh} & \sigma_{hh} & \sigma_{hh} & 0 & 0 & \sigma_{hh} \\ \sigma_{zz} & \sigma_{zz} & \sigma_{zz} & 0 & 0 & \sigma_{zz} \\ \sigma_{rh} & \sigma_{rh} & \sigma_{rh} & 0 & 0 & \sigma_{rh} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \sigma_{hz} & \sigma_{hz} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \sigma_{zr} & \sigma_{zr} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix} \quad (11)$$

Table 3: The calculated results by the 3D RVE micro-model

Results	ε_x	$\varepsilon_y=\varepsilon_z$	$\gamma_{xy}=\gamma_{zx}$	γ_{yz}
Deformation				
von-Mises stress				
Radial stress				
Hoop stress				
Axial stress				
R-H shear stress				
H-Z shear stress				

By extracting the calculated load-displacement data, the stress-strain curves of different loading types can be obtained as shown in Fig. 3. The elastic modulus along fiber direction E_x is the biggest one, which is 335.1GPa. The modulus of normal fiber direction E_y and E_z are both 212GPa. The shear modulus in xy plane is 72.4 GPa, and the modulus in yz and zx plane equals to 68GPa. From the predicted results, SiC_f/SiC composites show up obvious anisotropic properties of engineering elastic constants. Therefore, under the premise of knowing material components' properties, the engineering elastic constants of composites can be predicted by the RVE FEA model mentioned above.

Figure 3: The predicted modulus of tension and shear.

4 TRS CALCULATION AND ANALYSIS BASED ON MICRO-STRUCTURE FEA MODEL

On account of that PBC is not adapted to calculating TRS, the present section for predicting TRS would not use PBC. Meanwhile, to avoid the boundary influence on TRS during the thermal expansion [12-14], the relative larger model is created as shown in Fig. 4. The central zone is focused on, and TRS along 0° and 45° paths are extracted. The mesh seeds along two paths are set intensive and the local mesh size is $0.2\mu\text{m}$. The interphase thickness is meshed into three elements. The global mesh size is $0.45\mu\text{m}$. The element type is C3D8R [15] in Abaqus/standard. The material coordinates have radial, hoop and axial directions. The model is applied under the temperature of 1000°C to simulate material cooling to ambient temperature gradually. The coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) of SiC fiber, BN interphase and SiC matrix are $4.6 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$, $5.5 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$ and $4.6 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$ respectively [16].

Figure 4: The relative large micro-model and mesh size for TRS calculation.

Figure 5: The stress clouds: (a) radial stress, (b) hoop stress, (c) axial stress, and (d) radial-axial shear stress.

The four stress components of radial, hoop, axial and radial-axial shear stress are shown in Fig. 5. The other stress components are zero according to calculation. The four non-zero stress distributions along 0° and 45° directions are shown in Fig. 6, Fig. 7, Fig. 8 and Fig. 9.

Figure 6: Radial stress along (a) 0° , and (b) 45° direction.

Figure 7: Hoop stress along (a) 0° , and (b) 45° direction.

Figure 8: Axial stress along (a) 0°, and (b) 45° direction.

Figure 9: Radial-axial shear stress along (a) 0°, and (b) 45° direction.

5 EFFECT OF THE INTERPHASE YOUNG'S MODULUS ON TRS

5.1 Anisotropic Variation of Interphase Young's Modulus

Actually, many kinds of interphases are not homogeneous materials, which means that the elastic modulus at three normal directions are different from each other. And the interphase elastic properties are anisotropic. Hence, it is considered that E_{11} (fiber direction modulus) changes, E_{22} and E_{33} (fiber normal modulus) remain the same. The maximum stresses variation and computed results are shown in Fig. 10. With regard to radial and stress, anisotropic decreasing variation of interphase Young's modulus makes the interphase peak stress reduce, but the matrix peak stress increase. With respect to hoop stress, the variation regularity shows non-linear relationship. It implies that, if the interphase properties are anisotropic, the interphase peak TRS and matrix peak TRS would be affected obviously. Therefore, what kind of interphase and properties are important to the interphase and matrix peak TRS, which decide the material damage and strength. In addition, accurately predicting the peak TRS and distributions is the science basis of material design and material analysis.

Figure 10: The variation regularity of maximum stress along (a) 0°, and (b) 45° direction.

5.2 Effect of the Interphase Thickness on TRS

In general, the interphase thickness influences not only the interfacial bonding strength[18, 20] but also the TRS. In order to investigate the effect of interphase thickness on TRS, the micro- model is rebuilt with 200nm, 300nm and 500nm interphase thickness. The variation of maximum stresses are shown in Fig. 11. On the whole, interphase thickness thinning brings the benefit of radial and shear TRS reducing, and doesn't deteriorate the hoop and axial TRS. When the interphase thickness is 200nm, the interphase radial and shear stress decrease observably, and the matrix stress decrease slightly at the same time. The reduced TRS will contribute to strengthening the SiC_f/SiC composites. Precise prediction of TRS with batch parameters of micro-structural size is useful to material design and analysis.

Figure 11: The variation regularity of maximum stress along(a) 0°, and (b) 45°direction.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The 3D FEA model of micro-structure is applied to predict the stiffness and TRS for SiC_f/SiC composites through this research. Precise prediction of the equivalent stiffness and the TRS with batch parameters of micro-structural size is useful to material design and analysis. It is concluded that:

(1) Basing on RVE ideology with PBC, a 3D micro-structure FEA methodology is effective to calculate the equivalent stiffness for CMCs. The equivalent stiffness, six stress components and deformation can be precisely predicted by the model. The stresses at directions of displacement loading are expressed as a matrix form to give the zero and non-zero values. The difference of equivalent Young's modulus and shear modulus reflect the real anisotropic properties.

(2) On account of that PBC is not adapted to calculating TRS and the boundary influences on TRS during the thermal expansion, the new relative larger model based on 3D FEA which is created to predict TRS for CMCs. The model can accurately calculate the TRS distributions of fibre, interphase and matrix. The four stress components of radial, hoop, axial and radial-axial shear stress are not zero and analysed at 0° and 45° direction.

(3) Homogeneous variation of interphase Young's modulus is investigated for considering the effect of interphase elastic modulus on TRS during material design stage. The TRS distribution regularity doesn't change, as interphase Young's modulus varies. But the interphase peak stress reduces while Young's modulus decreases. Especially at 45° direction, reduction of interphase Young's modulus also makes for decreasing the matrix peak stress. Furthermore, the interphase elastic properties being anisotropic is considered by this model. If the interphase properties are anisotropic, the interphase peak TRS and matrix peak TRS would be affected obviously.

(4) The effect of interphase thickness on TRS is investigated by rebuilding the model. Interphase

thickness thinning brings the benefit of reduction of radial and shear TRS, and doesn't deteriorate the hoop and axial TRS. The reduced TRS will contribute to strengthening CMCs.

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